

dl-SERINE

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Mahajani and Ray (this *Journal*, 1956, 33, 455) described an intermediate compound, m.p. 62-64°, in their synthesis of serine. We now find that this substance is hydrated sodium acetate mixed with organic material from which no serine can be isolated. Therefore, the whole synthesis has been repeated. We describe below the revised process.

Methyleneaminoacetonitrile (3.4 g.) was suspended in alcohol (50 c.c.) and warmed to 50°, and in another flask paraformaldehyde (3 g.) was dissolved in absolute alcohol (25 c.c.) by warming (addition of two drops of sodium ethoxide solution described below helps dissolution). The paraformaldehyde solution was gradually added to the suspension of methyleneaminoacetonitrile in alcohol, taking care that temperature did not rise above 55°. A solution of sodium ethoxide (Na, 1.15 g. and alcohol, 25 c.c.) was added to the above mixture with shaking, temperature being kept at 54°. In an hour a clear solution resulted and the solution was maintained at 54° for 2 hours. The solution was then kept at 50° for 12 hours. It acquired a yellowish tinge and some sodium formate separated.

The solution was then concentrated *in vacuo* to about 30 c.c. when a slight evolution of ammonia was noticed. It was then mixed with 33 c.c. of 5% alcoholic KOH (95% alcohol was used) and refluxed on the steam-bath. After 2 hours, the mixture was left overnight at the room temperature. Next morning, solids [$\text{CH}_2=\text{N.C.I.}(\text{CH}_2\text{OH}).\text{COOK}$], were collected and washed with alcohol. The filtrate obtained at this stage was treated as under (B) below. The solids (1.5 to 1.8 g.) were dissolved in water (10 c.c.) and to the solution was added 10% H_2SO_4 (10 c.c.). The mixture was then heated to 90° for 2 hours when formaldehyde was evolved and the $\text{CH}_2=\text{N}$ group was completely hydrolysed. A part of the solution was neutralised with alkali and then made just acidic with HCl. The solution was spotted on Whatman filter paper No. 1, along with authentic samples of serine and glycine and run for 6 hours with the Partridge solvent (butanol-acetic acid-water). After drying in air the paper was sprayed with ninhydrin solution. The spot exactly corresponded to serine. R_f in HCl = 0.31 (serine and the substance), R_f = 0.24 in the case of both in H_2SO_4 . From the above, the structure of potassium salt was inferred.

From the bulk of the hydrolysed solution, serine can be isolated by any of the usual methods. After the removal of excess of H_2SO_4 with lead carbonate, filtration, and removal of lead with H_2S , the solution on concentration *in vacuo* gives serine, m.p. and mixed m.p. 246° (decomp.), yield 1.3 g.

Filtrate B: It was slowly evaporated on the water-bath and the residue was separately hydrolysed with 10% H_2SO_4 . The hydrolysed solution on chromatogram gave four spots, of which two were that of glycine and serine and the other two, we presume, were that of methyleneserine and methyleneglycine.

J. I. C. S., Sept., 1958.

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